

Vivid Visual Imagery Supports Autobiographical Recollection

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Abstract

This is a planned study, despite its language. It was part of a class. In this proposed study, we examine the relation between vividness of one's visual imagery and one's recollection of autobiographical memories. Despite the thousands of citations of David Marks' 1973 foundational paper of assessing one's visual imagery vividness, only a few had looked directly at visual imagery in connection with autobiographical memories. This study seeks to fill that gap. We are the first to utilize both the Vividness of Visual Imagery Questionnaire and the Autobiographical Recollection Test in a correlational study. We studied 100 college students (49 male, 48 female, 3 non-binary or prefer-not-to-say). We found that scores of VVIQ of Marks correlates to high scores of ART. Moreover, the correlation extends to all aspects of Autobiographical Recollection as modeled by Berntsen et al. T-tests confirm the findings by showing that the effect size is noteworthy: high scorers in VVIQ have higher means of ART scores -- and all 7 of ART subscales -- than low scorers of VVIQ. These findings suggest, *inter alia*, further possible explorations into the directionality of the relation of the two constructs, into connection between the processes underlying the generation of vivid imageries and the recollection of autobiographical memories, and into the development of clinical treatments to improve wellbeing.

Keywords: visual imagery, autobiographical memory, vividness, memory recollection, narrative coherence, narrative relevance

Introduction

This paper investigates the relation between the vividness of one's mental imageries and the robustness of one's autobiographical memories. Despite the abundance of research in both constructs, few has gone into how or if the two are related.

The scale to measure the vividness of one's mental imagery was developed by David Marks (1973) decades ago. It has since been cited thousands of times and used in many research papers to measure the construct it is designed for. The Vividness of Visual Imagery Questionnaire has proved reliable in measuring how vivid is the image that a person holds when they produce a particular thought: the sun, for example, or a person.

The second variable we examine is autobiographical recall. To measure how robustly one recalls events from one's past, Berntsen et. al. (2019) created the Autobiographical Recollection Test. The test measures the construct with questions that measure seven aspects of autobiographical recollection (the sense of Reliving the memory, Vividness, Visual Imagery, Scene, Narrative Coherence, Life-story relevance, and Rehearsal frequency).

On the relationship between autobiographical recollection and visual imagery qualities, in spite of the thousands of papers that have cited the VVIQ paper, only a handful have examined the relation directly. (The author found only one, and with the help of AI to browse Google Scholar's citations list found another.) One of these few, D'Argembeau and Van Der Linden (2006) looked at visual imagery's vividness and people's mental time travel. Although they did not directly at the construct of autobiographical recall, D'Argembeau and colleague found people with more detailed visual imageries also had more detailed past memories (and imaginations). Greenberg et. al. (2014) (prior to the ART scale development) took a more specific aim at

autobiographical recall and conducted experiments. They found one's visual imagery has a role in one's autobiographical recollection.

These findings suggest it is conceivable that the two constructs are related considerably. We are the first to directly test this relation. Moreover, we now have recent research that has made progress in assessing how people remember memories from their own individual past. Berntsen and colleagues (2019) has produced the aforementioned ART scale. The scale can be scored as one whole test. However, it can also be seen as seven subscales (*reliving, vividness, visual imagery, scene, narrative coherence, life-story relevance, and rehearsal*). As the first to deploy this 2019 research in the context of visual imageries, this paper seeks to fill the gap in the literature by investigating the specific relation between Vividness of Visual Imagery and Autobiographical Recollection. We hypothesize that the higher the vividness of one's visual imagery, the better one will recall autobiographical memories. In addition, we also hypothesize that the more vivid one's visual images are, the more highly one will score in all the seven dimensions autobiographical recall measured by the ART scale.

Methods

Participants

Participants are college students of large psychology classes. We randomly select 500 students (using Simple Random Sampling aided by computer program to generate random numbers), who may volunteer to participate. A possibility is a 20% response rate, in which scenario we obtain 100 students (49 male, 48 female, 3 non-binary or decline-to-say). with a mean age of 22 years ($SD = 4.2$). Also expected is 100% completion rate of those that do give consent to participate.

This proposed study has been approved by the IRB.

Materials and Procedures

The materials consist of an online questionnaire given at the first two weeks of the semester. This questionnaire is delivered via the Qualtrics platform. The participant is directed to a website where Qualtrics hosts the questionnaire. Prior to starting the questionnaire, the participant is asked whether they consent: they proceed only if they consent. After giving consent, the participant will need 30 minutes or less to complete the questionnaire. The sole questionnaire has only two parts: the first part is to measure vividness of mental imagery, and the second one is to measure recall of one's autobiographical memory.

To measure the vividness of one's mental images, we use the Vividness of Visual Imagery Questionnaire (Marks, 1973). This test has four scenarios of four questions, for a total of 16-item test. To make scoring easier, we modify the VVIQ in just one aspect: the scoring. The original VVIQ uses 1 for "as vivid as normal vision", with vividness decreasing to 5 for "no image at all: you only 'know' that you are thinking of the object." We reverse the ordering: 5 being the most vivid, and 1 being the least.

To measure how well one recalls past memories, we use the Autobiographical Recollection Test (Berntsen, 2019). The two questionnaires have also been included in the Appendix. The ART has 21 questions which is taken as one sequence; but the questions can be grouped into 7 subscales: Reliving, Vividness, Visual Imagery, Scene, Narrative Coherence, Life-story relevance, and Rehearsal. Reliving subscale measures how much the participant relives the event as if they are in the past event itself. The Vividness subscale gauges how vivid the participant's memory is. The Visual Imagery subscale assesses how visual the subject's memory

is. The Scene subscale measures the participant's recall of the spatial layout of the memory's scene. Narrative Coherence subscale measures the participant's sense of coherence in the narrative of the storylines in their memories. Life-story relevance subscale assesses how much the individual feels the memories are relevant to their life as a whole. The Rehearsal subscale measures how much the participant rehearses their memories.

Regarding the test order, whether VVIQ first or the ART first, each participant has a random chance of receiving the VVIQ as the first test or the ART. After the first test, the participant is given a 1 minute break. The next scale then appears, and the online sequence concludes after the participant completes that second part of the questionnaire. To analyze the data, the planned statistical analysis are given in the next section.

Results

Correlation Tests

After all the participants complete the questionnaires, we have their test scores. On these scores we perform correlation tests. We use Pearson's r to see whether there is a statistically-significant correlation between one's Vividness of Visual Imagery Questionnaire score and Autobiographical Recollection Test whole-scale score. For each of the 7 subscales of the ART scale, we also conduct correlation test against VVIQ score to see whether there is a correlation between VVIQ score and each component of Autobiographical Recollection. As such, we deploy a total of 8 correlation tests.

T-tests

To measure effect size and gather more evidence for or against our hypothesis, we conduct t-tests. To start, the t-tests, we take two groups by taking those beyond one standard

deviation of the mean: as such we have people with highly vivid visual imageries and their opposite end of vague or nonexistent imagery. (In case the group size are unequal, we will find another meaningful way to find two such opposing groups.) In a total 8 t-tests, we compare the means of the ART as a whole plus its 7 subscales.

Table

This is a table describing possible scores of the scales. (For simulation accuracies and precision, generative AI were used to help generate these hypothetical data. After the study has been conducted, with the real data we would not need to use such simulation.)

Variable	Means	SD	Min	Max
VVIQ total	3.42	.87	1	5
*				
ART total	4.83	.95	2.33	6.67
ART - Reliving	4.92	1.23	1.67	7.00
ART - Vividness	5.14	1.18	2.00	7.00
ART - Visual Imagery	5.27	1.20	2.33	7.00
ART - Scene	4.85	1.05	2.00	6.67
ART - Narrative Coherence	4.64	1.14	1.67	7.00
ART - Life-story Relevance	4.56	1.31	1.33	7.00
ART - Rehearsal	4.43	1.16	1.67	6.67

*(VVIQ is on a scale of 1-5, ART uses a scale of 1-7)

-The following are expected results.-

VVIQ and ART

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between VVIQ ($M=3.42$, $SD=.87$) scores and the ART ($M=4.83$, $SD=.95$) scores. For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between VVIQ and ART scores was found to be moderate and statistically significant, $r(98) = .67$, $p < .001$. These results suggest that visual imagery vividness and autobiographical recollection are quite positively related, with autobiographical recollection tending to be more robust among those with higher vividness of visual imagery.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in the scores of Autobiographical Recollection Test between the group with high vividness of visual imagery ($M=5.58$, $SD=.78$) and the low vividness group ($M=3.97$, $SD=.78$). There was a significant effect, $t(64)=9.42$, $p < .001$, $d=2.27$ such that people with vivid visual imageries produce higher scores on the ART scale. This result suggest that people with vivid visual imageries tend to be more robust in recalling their autobiographical events.

VVIQ and ART Subscale: Reliving

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between VVIQ ($M=3.42$, $SD=.87$) scores and the Reliving scores of the ART ($M=4.92$, $SD=1.23$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between VVIQ and ART scores was found to be moderate and statistically significant, $r(98) = .58$, $p < .001$. These results suggest that vividness of visual imagery and reliving memories are quite related positively, with people with higher vividness of visual imagery tending to relive the past event when they are recalling it.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in Reliving between people with high vividness ($M=5.69$, $SD=.81$) and those with low vividness ($M=4.13$, $SD=1.12$). There was a significant effect, $t(64)=6.48$, $p < .001$, $d=1.59$, such that people with vivid visual imageries produce higher scores on the ART scale. This result suggest that people with vivid visual imageries tend to also relive their past autobiographical events.

VVIQ and ART Subscale: Vividness***Correlations***

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between VVIQ ($M=3.42$, $SD=.87$) scores and the Reliving scores of the ART ($M=4.92$, $SD=1.23$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between VVIQ and ART-Reliving scores was found to be moderate and statistically significant, $r(98) = .58$, $p < .001$. These results suggest that vividness of visual imagery and reliving memories are positively related, with people with higher vividness of visual imagery tending to relive the past event when they are recalling it.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in Vividness of past autobiographical events between people with high general imagery vividness ($M=6.16$, $SD=.63$) and those with low general vividness ($M=4.02$, $SD=.92$). There was a significant effect, $t(64)=11.26$, $p < .001$, $d=2.71$, such that people with generally vivid visual imageries also have higher vividness when recalling past autobiographical events.

VVIQ and ART Subscale: Visual Imagery***Correlations***

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between VVIQ ($M=3.42$, $SD=.87$) scores and the Visual scores of the ART ($M=5.27$, $SD=1.20$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between VVIQ and ART-Visual scores was found to be strong and statistically significant, $r(98) = .76$, $p < .001$. These results suggest that vividness of visual imagery and the degree to which memories are visual are positively related quite strongly, with people with higher vividness of general visual image formation tending to have more visual autobiographical memories as well.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in Visual aspect of past autobiographical events between people with high general imagery vividness ($M=3.42$, $SD=.87$) and those with low general vividness ($M=4.09$, $SD=.99$). There was a significant effect, $t(64)=1.74$, $p < .001$, $d=2.59$, such that people that in general produce vivid visual imageries also are more visual specifically when surfacing autobiographical memories.

VVIQ and ART Subscale: Scene

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between VVIQ ($M=3.42$, $SD=.87$) scores and the Scene component of the ART ($M=4.85$, $SD=1.05$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between VVIQ and ART-Scene scores was found to be moderate and statistically significant, $r(98) = .65$, $p < .001$. These results suggest that vividness of visual imagery and the degree to which spatial layout is part of autobiographical memories are visual are positively related.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in Scene recall of autobiographical memories between people with high vividness of visual imagery ($M=5.63$, $SD=.74$) and those with low vividness

($M=3.96$, $SD=.86$). There was a significant effect, $t(64)=8.53$, $p < .001$, $d=2.09$, such that individuals high vivid visual imageries perform better in recalling the spatial layout of their autobiographical memories.

VVIQ and ART Subscale: Narrative Coherence

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between VVIQ ($M=3.42$, $SD=.87$) scores and the Narrative Coherence component of the ART ($M=4.64$, $SD=1.14$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between VVIQ and ART-Coherence scores was found to be moderate and statistically significant, $r(98) = .49$, $p < .001$. These results suggest that vividness of visual imagery and the degree to which autobiographical memories evoke a feeling of narrative coherence are moderately related.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in autobiographical Narrative Coherence between high vividness group ($M=5.31$, $SD=.89$) and low vividness group ($M=3.87$, $SD=.95$). There was a significant effect, $t(64)=6.44$, $p < .001$, $d=1.56$, such that people with high vividness of visual imageries tend to have a stronger feeling that their autobiographical narrative is coherent.

VVIQ and ART Subscale: Life-story Relevance

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between VVIQ ($M=3.42$, $SD=.87$) scores and the Life-story Relevance component of the ART ($M=4.56$, $SD=1.31$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between VVIQ and ART-Relevance scores was found to be moderate and statistically significant, $r(98) = .42$, $p < .001$. These results suggest that vividness of visual

imagery is moderately related to how much people feel their autobiographical memories are relevant to their life as a whole.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in the Life Story relevance aspect between high vividness group ($M=5.22$, $SD=1.02$) and low vividness group ($M=3.81$, $SD=1.13$). There was a significant effect, $t(64)=5.34$, $p < .001$, $d=1.30$, such that people with high vividness of visual imageries tend to exhibit the sense that their memories of past events define or are relevant to their life story or identity.

VVIQ and ART Subscale: Rehearsal

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between VVIQ ($M=3.42$, $SD=.87$) scores and the Rehearsal component of the ART ($M=3.89$, $SD=1.07$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between VVIQ and ART-Rehearsal scores was found to be moderate and statistically significant, $r(98) = .39$, $p < .001$. These results suggest that vividness of visual imagery is moderately related to how often people rehearse past events in their memories.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in the Life Story relevance aspect between high vividness group ($M=5.07$, $SD=.93$) and low vividness group ($M=3.89$, $SD=1.07$). There was a significant effect, $t(64)=4.85$, $p < .001$, $d=1.18$, such that people with high vividness of visual imageries tend to rehearse past events more often than individuals with low vividness.

Discussion

For this section, we assume the results are obtained as we expect above. To make language easier, we discuss as if the results are obtained as aforementioned -- since we have not conducted the study.

The study in question looks at the relation between the vividness of people's visual imageries and their recollection of autobiographical memories. We hypothesize that people with more vivid general visual imageries will exhibit more robust recall of autobiographical memories -- and will perform better across all aspects of autobiographical recollection. The empirical findings support both hypotheses. We found a positive correlation ($r=.67, p<.001$) that is significant statistically between VVIQ scores and the ART (the test as a whole) scores. Moreover, correlations of relatively similar strengths are found between VVIQ scores and the scores of each of the seven components of the ART (r values ranging from .39 to .76). In addition to correlation, we discovered a considerable effect size across ART and all its seven components. (with Cohen's d ranging from 1.18 to 2.71). Thus, the study's hypotheses are supported by the findings.

These results suggest that the two are related linearly. As hence our study's findings add to prior evidence (D'Argembeau and Van Der Linden, 2006) that support the relation between the two constructs. Our findings of consistent pattern of individual differences with a correlational study also align with prior research (Greenberg et. al, 2014) that with an experimental study highlighted visual imagery's role in memory recollection. It is conceivable that the mechanisms leading to visual imagery production and to the recollection -- or reconstruction -- of past events. This sheds light into the memory retrieval process and the influence or role of imagery

production process. It could be that they are built on shared processes. These may be elucidated by further studies, which are warranted by the results of this study.

One novel finding that makes this study particularly noteworthy is that visual imagery is quite correlated and has a considerable effect size on aspects such as narrative coherence ($r=.49$, $d=1.56$) and relevance ($r=.42$, $d=1.30$). So visual imagery is an excellent predictor variable for the criteria of the sense of relevance and coherence in one's mind and cognitive processes. This naturally inspires the author to create a new hypothesis that visual imagery vividness is perhaps required for the emotion or the sense of coherence and of relevance of memories. (e.g. Why is it "my" memory, or events that relate to "me" as opposed to an identity that I don't consider "me".)

We are the first to directly examine the empirical questions on the link between the scores of VVIQ and of ART. Moreover, our findings are not just statistically significant, the effect sizes warrant further investigation into the processes of memory recall and visual imageries.

In obtaining these findings, methodologically there is the issue of the appropriateness of statistical tests. The Likert scales are ordinal measures technically, hence using correlational test may be put into question. However, applying analysis with Pearson's r for Likert scores has proven to be reliable and robust that it has become common practice among researchers.

On limitations, there is an aspect in the Results section that is unlikely. We anticipate having 64 degrees of freedom, implying 66 people across both groups. However, if we assume the underlying population is normal, then it is unlikely that we will have 66 people beyond a distance of one standard deviation away from the mean (since roughly 68% of the Normal Curve is within one standard deviation). To address this, one way is to increase the sample size so we can get a high enough number of participants for the two extreme groups. Or, we may remove

the middle portion around the mean such that we end up with 66 people or a number acceptable for our tests.

Another limitation is, there was a risk of priming posed by the order of the questionnaires. This is why we ensured each participant has a random order: about half received VVIQ first, and the other half received the ART first (with a one-minute break in between).

This study merely sheds a light into a possible avenue of further inquiry. It does not by itself claim causes or directionality. The direction is not clear: does a vivid visual imagery system leads to a superior recall of autobiographical memories, or do better autobiographical memory recollection. Further studies are needed to ascertain the directionality. But we may be interested in possible third causal, mediator, or modulator variables behind the patterns we observe. Further studies may be conducted to elucidate whether one is able to modulate the vividness of one's visual imagery, and whether that modulation of vividness may impact past memory recollection, such as in sufferers of PTSD and other groups. This simple correlational study therefore could likely lead to improvements in treatments or therapies, and with that an increase in people's wellbeing.

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